

complexes are in progress and the details will be reported in due course.

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Equilibrium Studies between Ni(II)/Cu(II), 8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid and Histidine in Aqueous Solution

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8-HYDROXYQUINOLINE-5-SULPHONIC acid (HQSA) is well known chelating agent and its binary chelates have been studied quite extensively. However, so far the literature records very few solution equilibrium studies on the ternary complexes with HQSA as one of the ligands¹⁻⁶. During the present investigations, the pH-metric studies of the systems, Ni(II)/Cu(II) - HQSA - histidine (His) have been made.

Experimental

Metal salts (nitrates, AnalaR BDH) solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water and standardized with disodium salt of EDTA using murexide as indicator. HQSA (Kodak) was recrystallized from water and weighed out directly for

each investigation on account of its low solubility. Solution of histidine hydrochloride (BDH) was prepared by direct weighing and its strength was checked potentiometrically. Potentiometric titrations of the following solutions (total volume 50 ml) : (i) 10 ml (0.025 M) ligand, (ii) 10 ml (0.025 M) ligand + 10 ml (0.025 M), metal nitrate [M(II) - ligand, 1 : 1] where M(II) = Ni(II) or Cu(II) and (iii) 10 ml (0.025 M) each of primary and secondary ligands + 10 ml (0.025 M) metal nitrate [M(II) - primary ligand - secondary ligand, 1 : 1 : 1]; were carried out using a Systronics pH-meter. The ionic strength of the reaction mixtures was maintained approximately constant at 0.1 with potassium nitrate and the temperature at 30 ± 1° using a thermostat.

Results and Discussion

The dissociation constants of HQSA ($pK_1 = 4.06$, $pK_2 = 8.49$) and His (6.05, 9.17) were taken from literature^{4,7}. The pH-titration curves of solutions containing nickel nitrate and HQSA or His. HCl in equimolar proportions exhibit a sharp inflection at $m=2$ (m = moles of base added per mole of metal ion or ligand), followed by the buffer regions in the high pH-range. However, in case of solution containing copper nitrate, two inflections at $m=2$ and $m=3$ are observed. The inflection at $m=2$ in all cases indicate the formation of 1 : 1 complex. The inflection at $m=3$, or buffer region indicates the conversion of 1 : 1 complex into hydroxo derivative. In all these cases precipitation starts at $m \sim 2$.

The pH-titration curves of solutions containing nickel or copper nitrate in presence of equimolar concentrations of HQSA and His. HCl exhibit a sharp inflection at $m=4$, attributing the complete neutralization of both the protons of each of the ligands liberated as a result of chelation. All these curves run slightly above the corresponding 1 : 1 M(II)-HQSA titration curves in the beginning, which may be attributed to the presence of free tertiary and secondary amino groups in the His. HCl. This indicates that initially M(II)-HQSA (1 : 1) complexes are formed in the above systems. The lowering of these curves in comparison to the corresponding composite curves which is a measure of mixed ligand chelate formation, occurs after $m = 1.5$ in these systems, indicating the formation of the mixed ligand chelate species, which can only be 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes. The formation of the ternary complexes, thus, takes place in overlapping steps and through the formation of 1 : 1 M(II)-HQSA chelates. It also gets support by the analysis of the potentiometric data given below :

The formation of 1 : 1 : 1 mixed ligand chelate in the above systems may be represented as :

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NOTES

and the overall reaction for the formation of the 1 : 1 : 1 ternary chelate as :

where M^{2+} stands for metal ion, H_2A for HQSA and H_2L^+ for His.HCl. If K' and K'' are the equilibrium constants of reactions (i) and (ii) respectively, then

$$K' = \frac{[MAL^-][H^+]^2}{[MA][H_2L^+]} \quad \dots (1)$$

and

$$K'' = \frac{[MAL^-][H^+]^4}{[M^{2+}][H_2A][H_2L^+]} \quad \dots (2)$$

If T_M , T_A and T_L represent the total concentrations of the metal, the primary and secondary ligand species respectively and T_{OH} is the concentration of the base added to the reaction mixture during the titration and neglecting the concentrations of OH^- , A^{2-} and L^- in the pH-range studied, it follows that :

$$T_M = [M^{2+}] + [MA] + [MAL^-] \quad \dots (3)$$

$$T_A = [H_2A] + [HA^-] + [MA] + [MAL^-] \quad \dots (4)$$

$$T_L = [H_2L^+] + [HL] + [MAL^-] \quad \dots (5)$$

$$T_{OH} + [H^+] = 2[MA] + 4[MAL^-] + [HA^-] + [HL] \quad \dots (6)$$

In a 1 : 1 : 1 reaction mixture, using the equations (3)-(6) and relations for the dissociation constants of ligands and equilibrium constant (K_1) of the reaction, $M^{2+} + H_2A \rightleftharpoons MA + 2H^+$ it may be shown that :

$$a[M^{2+}]^2 + b[M^{2+}] - c = 0 \quad \dots (7)$$

where $a = K_1(1+y)/[H^+]^2$, $b = x+y+2xy$, $c = \{(4-m)T_M - [H^+]\}xy$, $x = 1 + k_1/[H^+]$ and $y = 1 + k'_1/[H^+]$

k_1 and k'_1 are the first dissociation constants of HQSA and His. HCl respectively. The values of K_1 ($\log K_{MA} = 11.92$ and 9.02 for Cu^{2+} -HQSA and Ni^{2+} -HQSA systems respectively) were taken from the literature⁸.

The equilibrium concentration of the free metal ions present in the reaction mixture was determined by solving equation (7). The concentrations of other species involved in the equilibrium relations were then calculated from the above equations together with the values of equilibrium constants K' and K'' . Further, the formation constant of the ternary complex (K_{MAL}) which may be defined as :

$$K_{MAL} = \frac{[MAL^-]}{[MA][L^-]} = \frac{K'}{k'_1 k'_2} \quad \dots (8)$$

and the overall stability constant of the mixed ligand chelate :

$$\beta_{MAL} = \frac{[MAL^-]}{[M^{2+}][A^{2-}][L^-]} = \frac{K''}{k_1 k_2 k'_1 k'_2} \quad \dots (9)$$

The values of the equilibrium and chelate formation constants of the ternary complexes are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EQUILIBRIUM AND CHELATE FORMATION CONSTANTS OF MIXED LIGAND CHELATES ($t = 30 \pm 1^\circ$, $\mu = 0.1$ KNO ₃)				
System	$-\log K'$	$-\log K''$	$\log K_{MAL}$	$\log \beta_{MAL}$
Cu(II)-HQSA-His	5.55 ± 0.12	6.18 ± 0.12	9.67 ± 0.12	21.59 ± 0.12
Ni(II)-HQSA-His	7.37 ± 0.13	10.90 ± 0.16	7.85 ± 0.16	16.87 ± 0.16

Other evidence supporting the formation of ternary complexes is also given by the colour change from the yellowish green of the 1 : 1 M^{2+} -HQSA binary complex and blue of the 1 : 1 M^{2+} -His binary complex to dark green in the presence of both the ligands. No precipitation at any stage in case of ternary systems also support the formation of ternary complexes.

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A Rapid Method for Selective Separation and Estimation of Chromium in Some Ores and Alloys by Hydrated Zirconium Dioxide Ion-Exchanger

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TANDON *et al.*¹ reported the high K_a -value ($> 10^4$) of chromium(VI) on hydrated zirconium dioxide which inspired us to study for selective separation of Cr(VI) from some ores and alloys using hydrated zirconium dioxide ion-exchanger.